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DocEnhance

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1. MAIN EVALUATION OUTCOMES

High student satisfaction

Students responding to the evaluation questionnaire gave the DocEnhance courses a global overall assessment rating of 5,18 on a scale of 6, with almost 9 out of 10 participants (86,0%) considering that they are very good or excellent. 98,9% of participants in the courses would recommend them to other students.

In line with these ratings, expected learning outcomes were met very well (51,8%) or completely (35,3%) in almost 9 out of 10 cases, and almost 9 out of 10 participants (87,2%) considered that they would be very useful or completely useful for their future career development.

Ratings were generally highest for the Career Management and Entrepreneurship Course, followed by the Data Stewardship Course and the Supervision Course.

Good adaptation of course guidelines, contents, learning materials and work methods to expected learning outcomes

Adaptation of course guidelines, contents, learning materials and work methods was globally considered to be very good or excellent, although there were slight differences between courses.

Course guidelines were best adapted in the Data Stewardship course, while course content adaptation was best in the Career Management and Entrepreneurship course. The course on Supervision rated highest in achievement of expected learning outcomes.

Courses required more time and effort than expected

6 out of 10 participants considered the time and effort required to achieve course objectives to be adequate (40,7%) or a bit more than expected (24,4%). Only 2 out of 10 students considered the time and effort needed to complete course objectives to be very little (1,20%) or a little (19,8%).

1.2. SUGGESTIONS FOR COURSE IMPROVEMENT

Suggestions made for general course improvement fell into the following categories: student profile; interaction; course content; learning materials and methods; and course duration.

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Student profile

Respondents suggested that the courses should be available for all Master's and PhD students, either as recommended or mandatory courses. Some believed that the courses should be tailored to the needs of different doctoral schools or disciplines/thematic bundles.

Interaction

Respondents from all three courses called for more interaction with the students, preferably with smaller groups in a face-to-face environment where Q&A sessions, debates and discussions are generally more dynamic and facilitate more synergies.

Respondents also pointed out the convenience of organising group discussions with people from the same areas of knowledge or at least similar disciplines in order to further enhance sharing of applicable know-how, practices and experiences.

Some respondents pointed out that student motivation and engagement could be enhanced if they received introductory information or pre-assignments before the sessions. In this same line of thought, other respondents called for follow-up schemes (permanent team/group/networking platform).

Course content

Students called for more practical tasks, discussions and examples.

Depending on the course, respondents suggested numerous specific contents to be included in the courses, re-designed, shortened or lengthened.

Learning materials and methods

Students referred to a diverse array of topics related to the DocEnhance learning materials and methods. Some stated their preference for live lectures over videos, and others preferred videos to articles. Some believed that there were too many mandatory reading materials.

Course duration

Most respondents pointed out that course duration should be extended in order to have the required time to cover the aspects addressed in greater depth.

1.3. REFLECTIONS ON KEY ISSUES REGARDING COLLABORATION BETWEEN THE ACADEMIC AND NON-ACADEMIC SECTORS

Evaluation questionnaires included an open-ended question on the key issues regarding collaboration between universities and the non-academic sector in doctoral education, based on respondents' personal experiences in doctoral education activities and in the pilot course taken.

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Two out of five respondents referred to the lack of communication and alignment between the orientations, expectations, standards and work cultures in the academic and non-academic sectors.

Another two out of five respondents expressed their views specifically with regard to collaboration between the academic and non-academic sectors in doctoral education, pointing out the importance of offering doctoral students the opportunity to experience non-academic work environments, work methods and processes in order to better adjust their roles to fit different sectoral needs. Respondents also referred to the need to valorise doctoral training in the non-academic sector, and to adjust doctoral programmes to labour market demands in order to create employment possibilities for PhDs in the non-academic sector.

One out of ten respondents referred to data-sharing, IPR and licensing as key issues for collaboration between the academic and non-academic sectors.

Another one out of ten said that they could not or did not know how to answer this question due to their lack of experience in the non-academic sector.

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2. INTRODUCTION

Between October 2021 and July 2022, the DocEnhance consortium put in place the second implementation of its three transferable skills pilot courses (Supervision, Data Stewardship, and Career Management and Entrepreneurship) within already existing PhD programmes at several experienced partner universities.

Each course was piloted for proof-of-concept by selected partner universities, chosen with the objective of maximizing diversity concerning cultural differences and the developmental stage of their PhD programmes, in order to assess the applicability of the concept across Europe.

The course on Data Stewardship was run by Karlstad University in Sweden and the University of Chemistry and Technology in the Czech Republic. Nova University of Lisbon in Portugal and Tampere University in Finland ran the course on Career Management and Entrepreneurship. The Supervision course was run by Tampere University in Finland, Matej Bel University in Slovakia, and University of Alcalá in Spain.

After each pilot course, participants and organisers were invited to complete a brief questionnaire on different aspects of the courses and to provide comments or suggestions for further development and improvement.

Feedback gathered from the first implementation of the pilot courses will be taken into consideration when refining the course concept and content for the final version to be made available in December 2022, and when elaborating the good practice guidelines for evaluation of PhD courses in transferable skills (Deliverable D4.6).

In order to collect feedback on the second implementation of the pilot courses, the pilot course evaluation questionnaires used in the first implementation of the pilot courses were adapted where needed and sent to participating organisers, educators/trainers and students by the respective piloting university. The responses collected were anonymously.

The questionnaires addressed the relevance of the courses and their perceived usefulness, and also inquired about modifications that could improve their quality.

The questionnaires were organised in a given set of close-ended questions referring to: practical organisation of the course piloting; course content, learning materials, methodology, learning outcomes and satisfaction in terms of relevance and outcomes.

The response options for a closed-ended question are exhaustive and mutually exclusive. The types of response for closed-ended questions are rate scale responses presented with a continuous scale based on 6 levels (in order to avoid the central tendency of the 3 when working with a 1-5 scale).

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Open-ended questions ask respondents to formulate his/her own answer in his/her own words, including comments and/or suggestions for improvement.

While the student response rate was 81,3%, few complete questionnaires were received from organisers and teachers. Due to lack of representativeness, no statistical analysis has been carried out and contributions from organisers and teachers have been included in the text where relevant.

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3. THE PILOTING UNIVERSITIES AND PILOT COURSES

The second implementation of the DocEnhance pilot courses was carried out between October 2021 and July 2022 at six selected university partners, chosen with the objective of maximizing diversity concerning cultural differences and the developmental stage of their PhD programmes, in order to assess the applicability of the DocEnhance concept across Europe.

UNIVERSITY OF CHEMISTRY AND TECHNOLOGY (CZECH REPUBLIC)

The University of Chemistry and Technology Prague (UCT) is one of the smaller and more accessible research institutions in Europe. Following more than two centuries of tradition, UCT represents a melting pot where scientific discovery meets a friendly study environment with a highly valued personal approach. UCT is a first-rate study and research facility in the field of technical chemistry. The university takes pride in the effective combination of practical preparation with top-quality scientific equipment combined with hands-on laboratory instruction and a personal touch in its teaching style. The university consists of four faculties: Chemical Technology, Environmental Technology, Food and Biomechanical Technology, and Chemical Engineering. Each offers a broad range of bachelor, master's, and PhD programmes in English in the fields of material engineering, petroleum technology and alternative fuels, biotechnology, microbiology, cosmetics, and others. The number of students is usually around 4,000 with about 700 PhD students at a 1:20 teacher-to-student ratio. UCT currently cooperates with more than 200 academic institutions around the globe both in student exchange and research activities. UCT has participated in 32 projects within the 7th Framework programme (FP7), both within research and educational topics. UCT has recently invested more than €22 million from national and European structural funds in advanced instrumentation used mainly by master's and PhD students for completing their degrees. This investment thus contributes to enhancing UCT's competitiveness in the European research environment and in the further improvement of student training.

TAMPERE UNIVERSITY (FINLAND)

Tampere University (TAU) provides a space for doctoral researchers to develop both their research and innovation activities and transferable skills in multidisciplinary learning and lifelong partnerships. The developed applications of TAU aim to benefit industry, business and the public sector. The university continually strengthens the culture of international collaboration and digitalisation of the campus and promotes sustainable societal renewal, social innovation and spear-head research in health, technology, and social sciences. Some 220 doctorates are defended on a yearly basis at TAU. The TAU Doctoral School (est. 2011) is an institutional-level doctoral training expert. The Doctoral School supports the thorough and interdisciplinary academic expertise and employability of all doctoral researchers. Together with doctoral programmes, the school offers excellent, systematic and up-to-date training to all researchers at all career levels. The Doctoral School's courses and other

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interdisciplinary events bring together the 2200 doctoral-level researchers across all faculties and their 23 doctoral programmes.

NOVA UNIVERSITY OF LISBON (PORTUGAL)

The NOVA University of Lisbon (UNL) is a public HEI situated in Lisbon with around 20,000 students and 2,000 PhD candidates. The UNL Doctoral School was launched in 2013 with two specific aims: to reinforce the personal and professional development of PhD students through transferable skills training and to establish an open space for networking and discussion among PhD students and supervisors from the university's nine schools. So far, the doctoral school offers 13 courses for students, open to researchers and non-academic staff, and one course on supervisory skills. The UNL Doctoral School has disseminated its programme and outcomes nationally and internationally and its ambition is now to network with similar institutions in Europe. Additionally, a consortium of HEIs and non-academic organizations (stakeholders in the private and public sectors) represents an employment-oriented opportunity to establish bridges with the world outside academia's walls.

MATEJ BEL UNIVERSITY (SLOVAKIA)

Matej Bel University in Banská Bystrica (UMB) is the main comprehensive HEI in Central Slovakia. It has 600 university teachers and researchers and 9,000 students studying at six faculties: Economics, Humanities, Natural Sciences, Political Sciences and International Relations, Education, and Law. UMB is the first Slovak university to receive the "HR Excellence in Research" award. International cooperation has been rapidly developing in recent years mainly through numerous EU programmes including FPs. UMB is currently implementing three H2020 projects, Erasmus+ projects and playing a pivotal role in Vision2020, which is a prestigious network of European universities and SMEs aiming at higher participation in H2020. UMB has an advanced infrastructure with sufficient technical equipment that has been improved in recent years with the financial support of European structural funds. All university premises have access to world databases such as Cambridge Journals: Humanities and Social Sciences, Emerald, Scopus, Science Direct, Springer Link, Web of Knowledge, Wiley Online Library, etc. UMB provides ample space and facilities for research, teaching and networking. International cooperation has been rapidly developing in recent years mainly through participation in numerous EU projects under FP5, FP6, FP7 and H2020. UMB furthermore has long-term experience in participation in many other research projects financed by various grant schemes, for example NIL funds, OSF, CEEPUS, Interreg, Erasmus, British KHF, American Express, EEA GRANTS, VISEGRAD, etc.

UNIVERSITY OF ALCALÁ (SPAIN)

Founded in 1499, the University of Alcalá (UAH) is a public university with more than 28,000 students and 1,900 academic staff. It currently runs 36 degree and 45 master's courses on its three campuses in the fields of Health, Social Science and Law, Humanities, Science and Engineering and Computer Science. UAH is located in an industrial environment that provides an advantageous situation for the development of research projects in

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collaboration with private industries. UAH has obtained funding for eight projects under H2020, one of which is coordinated by UAH. The university has furthermore obtained funding for 29 projects under FP7, four of them as coordinator, and for 28 projects and contracts under different R&I programmes and initiatives in Europe, four of them funded under the Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme with two projects coordinated by UAH. The UAH Doctoral School has 29 doctoral programmes with 1404 students enrolled in the 2017-18 academic year. Almost 25% of them are foreign students. UAH has participated in 20+ Erasmus+ Programmes from 2014. UAH has a relevant role in the European PhD Hub project by providing collaborations from the business sector and other stakeholders. UAH is also involved in C3QA, an Erasmus+ Programme to extend the European PhD framework to other non-EU countries such as Ukraine, Mongolia, Armenia, and Kazakhstan. In addition, UAH has led an MSCA Co-fund action entitled "Got Energy Talent", in which collaboration among the business and academia sectors was enhanced by sending PhD researchers out of Spain in order to develop and collect information related to the energy field.

KARLSTAD UNIVERSITY (SWEDEN)

Karlstad University (KAU) is a civic university located in central Sweden. It currently hosts around 70 education programmes and 900 courses within humanities, social studies, science, technology, teaching, health care and the arts. At present, the university has approximately 16,000 students, 800 academic staff and 400 support staff across its campuses in Karlstad and Arvika. KAU's research programmes have a broad scope, positioning it well for engagement in successful collaborations with a range of partners from within the academy and beyond, from major national and international companies, such as Stora Enso and Billerud Korsnäs, to public bodies, such as the Värmland region. This strongly rooted collaborative approach with public and private actors provides the university with significant expertise in, and opportunities for, the utilisation of research and the wider employability of researchers. KAU offers a range of innovative doctoral training programmes in transferable skills, several of which are run in co-operation with other universities nationally and internationally. These include the Innovation Office Fyrklövern's PhD course "Impact and Utilisation of Research", which helps students understand how to benefit wider society through their research, and which covers areas such as Intellectual Property Rights, funding policy, entrepreneurship, and "research pitching" using the NABC method. In addition, KAU coordinated the Erasmus+ Strategic Partnership "TRANSPER: a Transnational Project to Enhance the Employability of Researchers", which sought to develop transferable skills that serve participants well in both academic and non-academic careers.

The three pilot courses were completed by a total of 107 students, of which 87 (81,3%) responded the evaluation questionnaire completely or partially.

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Data Stewardship Course				
Course dates	Piloting University	No. Participants (Students)	No. Respondents (Students)	Response Rate
11/04/2022-12/05/2022	Karlstad University (Sweden)	1	1	100,0%
01/03/2022-30/04/2022	University of Chemistry and Technology (Czech Republic)	22	22	100,0%

Career Management & Entrepreneurship Course				
Course dates	Piloting University	No. Participants (Students)	No. Respondents (Students)	Response Rate
07/04/2022-21/04/2022	Tampere University (Finland)	10	10	100,0%
03/2022-04/2022	Universidade Nova de Lisboa (Portugal)	15	8	53,3%

Supervision Course				
Course dates	Piloting University	No. Participants (Students)	No. Respondents (Students)	Response Rate
17/05/2022-10/06/2022	Universidad de Alcalá (Spain)	32	26	81,3%
11/05/2022-01/06/2022	Tampere University (Finland)	13	13	100,0%
04/05/2022-26/05/2022	Univerzita Mateja Bela V Banskej Bystrici (Slovakia)	14	7	50,0%

4. QUANTITATIVE RESULTS

4.1. SUMMARY OF RESPONSES

The eight closed-ended questions included in the student questionnaires were rate scale responses presented with a continuous scale based on 6 levels (in order to avoid the central tendency of the 3 when working with a 1-5 scale).

Global ratings ranged from 3,33 to 5,29, with an average of 4,95. All ratings improved with the exception of the adaptation to the expected learning outcomes of the work methods used, which declined only slightly (0,09 points less). In the case of the rating given to the time and effort needed to achieve the course objectives, the lower rating is actually an improvement as it reflects that course participants needed less time and effort than in the first implementation of the pilot courses.

Question	Global rating 2022	Global rating 2021	Variation 2021-2022
To what degree did you achieve your expected learning outcomes?	5,29	4,75	> 0,54
In your opinion, to what extent are the course contents adapted to your expected learning outcomes?	5,26	4,81	> 0,45
Do you think that the learning outcomes of the course will be useful for your future career development?	5,24	5,09	> 0,15
In your opinion, to what extent are the learning materials adapted to your expected learning outcomes?	5,22	4,98	> 0,24
In your opinion, to what extent are the course guidelines adapted to your expected learning outcomes?	5,18	5,00	> 0,18
Please give the course an overall assessment	5,16	4,96	> 0,20
In your opinion, to what extent are the work methods adapted to your expected learning outcomes?	4,88	4,97	< 0,09
How much time and effort did you need to achieve the course objectives?	3,33	3,75	< 0,42
AVERAGE RATING	4,95	4,78	> 0,17

With regards to each specific course, the average rating, overall assessment, usefulness, course contents, work methods and achievement of expected learning outcomes were highest for the Career Management and Entrepreneurship Course (5,36, 5,29, 5,53, 5,53, 5,18 and 5,35 respectively), followed by the Data Stewardship Course (5,17, 5,13, 5,48, 5,35, 4,30 and 5,09 respectively) and the Supervision Course (5,10, 5,13, 5,02, 5,13, 5,07 and 5,22 respectively).

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Usefulness for future career development and course guidelines were the two most important items for students participating in the course on Data Stewardship, while Career Management and Entrepreneurship students ranked usefulness and contents in the two highest positions. For students participating in the Supervision course, achievement of expected learning outcomes was highest.

The time and effort needed need to achieve the course objectives were reported to be between adequate and a little more than expected in all three cases.

All participants in the courses would recommend them to other students, except for one participant in the Supervision course.

4.2. DETAILED RESPONSES

In order to better evaluate the feedback gathered from the closed-ended questions for future refining of each of the pilot courses, detailed student responses are collected in the following pages.

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To what degree did you achieve your expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all; 2: a little; 3: somewhat; 4: well; 5: very well; 6: completely)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Data Stewardship	23	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	17,4%	56,5%	26,1%	5,09
Career Management & Entrepreneurship	17	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	11,8%	41,2%	47,1%	5,35
Supervision	45	0,0%	0,0%	2,2%	8,9%	53,3%	35,6%	5,22
TOTAL	85	0,0%	0,0%	1,2%	11,8%	51,8%	35,3%	5,21

Participants' expectations regarding the learning outcomes of the DocEnhance courses were generally satisfied to a high degree: 9 out of 10 reported that their expectations had been met very well (51,8%) or completely (35,3%). These results are two points higher than those obtained after the first implementation of the pilot courses in 2021.

Satisfaction levels were very similar among participants in the three courses. 82,6% of participants in the Data Stewardship course considered that their expectations had been met very well (56,5%) or completely (26,1%). In the case of the course on Career Management & Entrepreneurship 88,2% considered that they achieved their expectations very well (41,2%) or completely (47,1%). With respect to the course on Supervision, 88,9% of participants considered that their expected learning outcomes were met very well (51,8%) or completely (35,3%).

The course on Career Management & Entrepreneurship received the highest global score (5,35), although this score was slightly lower (- 0,11 points) than that obtained after the first implementation of the pilot course.

The courses on Data Stewardship and Supervision improved their global scores with respect to those received after the first implementation of the pilot courses: 1,15 and 0,33 points higher in the case of Data Stewardship and Supervision, respectively.

In your opinion, to what extent are the course guidelines adapted to your expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all; 2: a little; 3: somewhat; 4: well; 5: very well; 6: completely)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Data stewardship	23	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	4,3%	43,5%	52,2%	5,48
Career Management & Entrepreneurship	17	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	11,8%	47,1%	41,2%	5,29
Supervision	47	0,0%	0,0%	6,4%	12,8%	55,3%	25,5%	5,00
TOTAL	87	0,0%	0,0%	3,4%	10,3%	50,6%	35,6%	5,18

DocEnhance course guidelines were generally considered to be very well (50,6%) or completely (35,6%) adapted to participants' expected learning outcomes. This result is 13,1 points higher than after the first implementation of the pilot courses in 2021.

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Satisfaction levels were highest among participants in the course on Data Stewardship. 95,7% of participants considered that the course guidelines were very well (43,5%) or completely (52,2%) adapted to their expected learning outcomes.

88,2% of participants in the course on Career Management & Entrepreneurship considered that the course guidelines were very well (47,1%) or completely (41,2%) adapted to their expected learning outcomes.

Results for the course on Supervision indicate that 80,9% of participants consider that the course guidelines were very well (55,3%) or completely (25,5%) adapted to their expected learning outcomes.

The courses on Data Stewardship and Career Management & Entrepreneurship improved their global scores with respect to those received after the first implementation of the pilot courses: + 0,48 and + 0,06 points, respectively. The global score for the Supervision course remained unaltered.

In your opinion, to what extent are the work methods adapted to your expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all; 2: a little; 3: somewhat; 4: well; 5: very well; 6: completely)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Data stewardship	23	4,3%	0,0%	8,7%	43,5%	34,8%	8,7%	4,30
Career Management & Entrepreneurship	17	0,0%	5,9%	0,0%	11,8%	35,3%	47,1%	5,18
Supervision	46	0,0%	0,0%	4,3%	19,6%	41,3%	34,8%	5,07
TOTAL	86	1,2%	1,2%	4,7%	24,7%	38,8%	30,6%	4,88

With respect to the adaptation of course work methods to expected learning outcomes, almost 7 out of 10 participants thought they were very well or completely adapted.

Satisfaction levels were highest among participants in the course on Career Management & Entrepreneurship. With a global score of 5,18, 8 out of 10 participants considered that the work methods were very well (35,3%) or completely (47,1%) adapted to their expected learning outcomes.

Participants reported that the work methods used in the Supervision courses were very well (41,3% and 34,8%) or completely (21,1% and 37,9%) adapted to expected learning outcomes.

The Data Stewardship course received the lowest ratings, with only 34,8% of participants who believed that the work methods applied were very well adapted to expected learning outcomes, and only 8,7% who considered that they were completely adapted.

In comparison to the results obtained after the first implementation of the pilot courses, only the global score for the Supervision course improved slightly (+ 0,10 points).

In your opinion, to what extent are the course contents adapted to your expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all; 2: a little; 3: somewhat; 4: well; 5: very well; 6: completely)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Data stewardship	23	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	8,7%	47,8%	43,5%	5,35
Career Management & Entrepreneurship	15	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	13,3%	20,0%	66,7%	5,53
Supervision	46	0,0%	0,0%	6,5%	15,2%	37,0%	41,3%	5,13
TOTAL	84	0,0%	0,0%	3,6%	13,1%	36,9%	46,4%	5,26

Participants' satisfaction with course content was highest in the Data Stewardship course: 9 in 10 considered the course content very well (47,8%) or completely adapted (43,5%) to their expected learning outcomes. In fact, its global score increased by 1,3 points with respect to the first implementation of the pilot course.

The Career Management & Entrepreneurship received the highest global score (5,53). 86,7% of participants believed that the course content was very well (20,0%) or completely (66,7%) adapted to their expected learning outcomes.

Participants' in the Supervision course reported slightly lower levels of satisfaction with respect to the first implementation of the pilot course. The global score received in the second round of the course is 0,15 points lower.

In your opinion, to what extent are the learning materials adapted to your expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all; 2: a little; 3: somewhat; 4: well; 5: very well; 6: completely)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Data stewardship	23	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	17,4%	30,4%	52,2%	5,35
Career Management & Entrepreneurship	17	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	23,5%	17,6%	58,8%	5,35
Supervision	46	0,0%	2,2%	6,5%	10,9%	39,1%	41,3%	5,11
TOTAL	86	0,0%	1,2%	3,5%	15,1%	32,6%	47,7%	5,22

The learning materials best adapted to the expected learning outcomes were those used in the Data Stewardship course: 8 out of 10 participants considered them to be very well adapted (30,4%) or completely adapted (52,2%).

Participants in the Supervision course thought that the learning materials were very well adapted (39,1%) or completely adapted (41,3%).

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In the case of the course on Career Management & Entrepreneurship, 17,6% considered the learning materials to be very well adapted and another 58,8% believed they were completely adapted.

The global score received in the second round of the Career Management & Entrepreneurship course is 0,11 points lower than after the first round, while the courses on Data Stewardship and Supervision improved by 0,82 and 0,06 points respectively.

How much time and effort did you need to achieve the course objectives? (1: very little; 2: a little; 3: adequate; 4: a bit more than expected; 5: very much; 6: too much)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Data stewardship	23	0,0%	21,7%	26,1%	34,8%	13,0%	4,3%	3,52
Career Management & Entrepreneurship	17	0,0%	5,9%	41,2%	35,3%	17,6%	0,0%	3,65
Supervision	46	2,2%	23,9%	47,8%	15,2%	8,7%	2,2%	3,11
TOTAL	86	1,2%	19,8%	40,7%	24,4%	11,6%	2,3%	3,33

Four out of 10 participants considered the time and effort required to achieve course objectives to be adequate (40,7%), another 4 out of 10 thought that the time and effort required was a bit more than expected (24,4%), very much (11,6%) or too much (2,3%), and only 2 out of 10 reported that the time and effort required was a little (19,8%) or very little (1,2%).

Most time and effort was required of participants in the Data Stewardship and Career Management & Entrepreneurship courses (52% said it was a little more than expected, very much, or too much).

26,1% of participants in the Supervision course and 21,7% of participants in the Data Stewardship course required very little or little time and effort, while this was the case for only 5,9% of participants in the course on Career Management & Entrepreneurship.

Do you think that the learning outcomes of the course will be useful for your future career development? (1: not at all; 2: very little; 3: somewhat; 4: a lot; 5: very much; 6: completely)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Data Stewardship	23	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	4,3%	43,5%	52,2%	5,48
Career Management & Entrepreneurship	17	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	5,9%	35,3%	58,8%	5,53
Supervision	46	0,0%	4,3%	2,2%	13,0%	47,8%	32,6%	5,02
TOTAL	86	0,0%	2,3%	1,2%	9,3%	44,2%	43,0%	5,24

When asked if the learning outcomes obtained through the DocEnhance courses will be useful for their future career development, almost 9 out of 10 participants (87,2%)

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considered that they would be very useful or completely useful. This result reflects a 5 point increase with respect to the results obtained after the first implementation of the pilot courses.

This is especially the case with the courses on Data Stewardship and Career Management & Entrepreneurship and Supervision, considered to be very or completely useful in 95,7% and 94,1% of the cases, respectively.

On the other end of the balance, 6,5% of respondents pointed out that the Data Stewardship course would not be useful for their future career development at all or very little.

Participants gave the courses a global score of 5,24, ranging from a score of 5,53 in the case of the course on Career Management & Entrepreneurship and of 5,02 in the case of the course on Supervision.

Please give the course an overall assessment. (1: very poor; 2: poor; 3: average; 4: good; 5: very good; 6: excellent)								
Course	Replies	1	2	3	4	5	6	Global score
Data Stewardship	23	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	13,0%	60,9%	26,1%	5,13
Career Management & Entrepreneurship	17	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	11,8%	47,1%	41,2%	5,29
Supervision	46	0,0%	2,2%	2,2%	10,9%	50,0%	34,8%	5,13
TOTAL	86	0,0%	1,2%	1,2%	11,6%	52,3%	33,7%	5,16

The global score obtained by the DocEnhance courses is 5,16, with almost 9 out of 10 participants (86,0%) considering that they are very good or excellent. These results reflect an improvement with respect to those obtained after the first implementation of the pilot courses, when the global score was 4,96 and 78,2% of participants rated the courses as very good (52,3%) or excellent (33,7%).

The course on Career Management & Entrepreneurship received the highest ratings, with a global score of 5,29. 88,2% of participants believed the course to be excellent (41,2%) or very good (46,1%).

The Data Stewardship course received a global score of 5,13 and 87% of participants considered it to be very good (60,9%) or excellent (26,1%)

84,8% of respondents rated the Supervision course as excellent (34,8%) or very good (50,0%). The course also received a global score of 5,13.

When asked if they would recommend the courses to other students, only one participant of a total of 86 responded 'no'.

5. QUALITATIVE RESULTS

Qualitative results from the student questionnaires are presented separately for each course as the information provided through the open questions is to be taken into consideration when refining the courses for the second implementation of the piloting process. Literal responses to the open-ended questions have been included as they enrich the feedback received.

5.1 PILOT COURSE 1: DATA STEWARDSHIP

What learning outcomes did you expect to achieve from the course?

The Data Stewardship course was designed with the prime objective of providing students with an understanding of data management and data management tools.

In line with this general aim, students' expected learning outcomes focused mainly on data management (types of data; formats; how to write a data management plan; how to properly create, save, arrange, store, retrieve, share, reuse and publish data; data lifecycle; legal framework), although they also mentioned data processing, open research, available tools (software, platforms and licenses) to support researchers, as well as best practices and case studies. A few students also expressed an interest in networking opportunities and job opportunities in the non-academic sector.

What are the three most important things that you have learned as a result of participating in this course?

When asked what were the three most important things that they learned as a result of participating in the Data Stewardship course, students focused on the following aspects:

- Available resources (licenses/licensing, repositories, database platforms, data search engines, apps, etc.): 27,8%
- The importance of the Data Management Plan (DMP), how to develop and use it: 20,37%
- Data storage and archiving techniques: 20,37%
- Metadata and readme files – 16,7%
- FAIR principles/rules: 9,3%
- Open research data and data sharing: 5,6%

What parts of this course were the most relevant for you?

Students specifically mentioned modules 1 and 2 as the most relevant parts of the Data Stewardship course in 21,7% and 26,1% of the cases, respectively. One student stated that “the discussion in Module 2 was relevant to fixate on what we learned in Module 1”.

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Regarding Module 1, students especially pointed out the information provided on data visualisation; practical examples of data management tools (python, R, electronic lab notebooks, repositories). Module 1 was considered to be “very informative with plenty additional information (recommending readings and food for thoughts)”.

Regarding Module 2, students focused especially on the group discussions and practical/interactive activities carried out with other participants, as they were considered to be “very beneficial because of sharing the experience and solving problems together”.

Specific subjects addressed in the course which were considered to be most relevant included those covered in the seminars on "Structuring, documenting, and metadata" and "Data storage, file formats, and the FAIR principles" (data management plan, data storage and archiving techniques, metadata and readme files, among others). Participants also highlighted the relevance of data sensitivity, citing, licenses and copyrights.

What parts of this course were the least relevant for you?

26,1% of students responded that all parts of the course were relevant.

13% of students believed that the presentation on spectroscopic and crystallographic data processing was too specific and not applicable to all participants.

More experienced students considered the sessions on file formats, data storage, data visualisation, data evaluation, licensing and FAIR principles to be the least relevant, as they claimed to be familiar with these issues already.

How can we improve these aspects of the course? Comments/suggestions regarding course methodology, course content and/or learning materials. Additional comments/suggestions.

Teachers referred to setting up more time for discussion and also suggested that “a good addition might be some concise handouts for students with FAIR guidelines, metadata and README talking points, etc. which the students can quickly reference whenever they want, when discussing or assessing a dataset.”

Students made numerous suggestions for general course improvement. The responses have been grouped into the following categories: student profile; interaction; less theory, more practice; speakers; course content; learning materials; course duration.

Student profile

- “Module 1 should be available for all MSc/PhD students at the start of the academic year as a voluntary, but recommended course”.
- “I would strongly recommend to make this course obligatory for all PhD students (somewhere in the beginning of the first year, before they start working on their

projects), and maybe even optional for Master students who may decide to continue their education as PhD candidates”.

Interaction

- “Smaller groups, groups of 4 or 5 were a bit dispersing”.
- “If using a hybrid format, it might be worth connecting everyone through MS Teams at the start of the Module 2 (or even Module 1)”.
- “I would shorten some group discussion parts or suggest a controlled discussion”.
- “Better handling of online participation (if it even is possible). Especially during doctoral studies, it can happen that one really cannot attend in person”.
- “Less discussion or group projects in Module 2. In some parts, it seemed a little bit forced”.
- “Some parts of Module 2 could be done could be done separately (individually) with the common discussion at the end.”
- “It would be helpful to distribute a brief introductory (can be a few bullet points) print page amongst the attendees, before the start of each session. I believe it will help the attendees not to lose concentration even during the most complicated part of the lecture/session”.
- “It might be beneficial to distribute the pre-assignment text more than 30 min before the lecture starts”.
- “At the start of Module 2 ask the attendees about their major aim for the course, possibly through a questionnaire, it will make the attendees read the course contents thoroughly in advance and will keep them engaged during the follow-up sessions”.
- “Create a permanent team/group/network/platform of data stewardship course alumni, who can keep in touch and can share their ideas from time to time”.
- “Take compulsory follow-up feedback from the attendees, with a special focus on the outcome of their discussion with their peers, and if they could implement any part of the course in their research/professional career. This would help to bring new ideas to the course”.

Less theory, more practice

- “Maybe a bit more time with more applied exercises would be great”.
- “Spend more time on practicing of data management”.
- “General tips on what should and should not be in graphs, axis, legends ... and so on”.
- “My suggestion is to add more practical tasks related to data processing pipelines”.
- “Include more practical tasks (for self-study)”.
- “More time for the presential classes with more exercises”.
- “During Module 2, it could be better if more examples are given of what we learn in theory”.
- “Working in groups is ok, but I would recommend adding more frame to the workshop. For example, start with the DMP, give each group an imaginary topic of research and let them work on the DMP. Then, generate a random results file for each group and practise the archiving on the generated data. We had sample sets, but it was mostly about

moving files somewhere and we didn't get our hands "inside" so to speak. If we could follow the project from start to the end, it would be a bit better".

- "There was quite a lot of theory. I understand that it is difficult to provide practical examples because all of us are from different fields and it is difficult to generalize, but I would have really liked to see how a good data management plan or well-organized data look like and hear some comments why it is so. We discussed a lot of things in groups during the second module, which was very useful for understanding problems of different scientific fields, but we did not get a lot of hands-on experience".

Speakers

- "The English of some speakers was not as good as I expected it to be".
- "Select speakers who do not have a problem with English".
- "Lecturers should know the terminology (e.g. archiving, not archivizing) and pronunciation (e.g. giga bytes, not [džigabajts]; various, not [vírius]) of important words in their respective presentations. It is understandable, that some non-native speakers might have a hard time with English pronunciation, but I believe that they should at minimum know the pronunciation of the words in their presentation".
- "I appreciated the diversity of speakers, it was refreshing".
- "The most interesting part is that the presentations were from people of different fields and backgrounds making it easier for all of us to get a different perspective on the same topic".

Couse content

- "I would appreciate some lectures about the use of electronic laboratory notebooks".
- "Include more general programs for creating graphs".
- "Maybe add a part about how to deal with ethical requirements from the university that are not flexible and do not allow open data".
- "Include representation of scientific data (such as spectroscopic data) at beginning of Module 2".
- "In Module 2, adding discussions about job opportunities in both academic and non-academic areas after a PhD will be more helpful".
- "Add a topic discussion on job opportunities in both academic and non-academic areas after a PhD".
- "One thing was repeated three times - FAIR data. First it was in Module 1 - which was fine. Then in Module 2 - fine. But in the next lesson, the same topic was practiced by another lecturer".
- "The data processing part could have been shorter or more varied, in my opinion it would suffice to show just a few examples what a good and bad processed data look like, what you should generally watch out for, etc.".
- "The law related to data could have been more interactive".
- "There were parts which could be more deeply explained such as sharing and licensing research data, and the data management plan".
- "We did go through .csv, maybe .txt and some spectroscopic files, but there are plenty of other basic formats which were not covered, and I think especially picture formats

are important for our everyday work. We didn't get any info on pros and cons of these formats".

- "I am not sure if the connection is obvious but, I think it would be very interesting in the last part of Module 2 that the students have the opportunity to talk about their CV and if there could be some representative to help them make it more clear and structured. I believe a CV is the main "personal metadata" of each of us and I see it as connected with these courses".
- "Make sure that lectures and group works of one expert don't overlap with other experts' lecture and group work. During the course of Module 2, we were supposed to effectively re-tell more than 4 times the story regarding our data: what we do, what data we have, are the data confidential ... the same for presentations regarding FAIR principle, which was repeated more than 5 times and not only by mention but usually in the form of an exercise, group work or a discussion."

Learning materials

- "Revise the key points from Module 1 in a brief introductory slide/s, during the kick-off session of Module 2. I believe it will help the attendees to get into the course instantly."
- "I think some video in module 1 could be refreshed, or maybe it could be better if the information is provided by text (definitions from any book)".
- "In Module 1, some YouTube videos are boring and can be made more interesting".
- "I like the video method with possible more reading, I have found the links to reading good for those who wish to learn from the course".
- "As for the exam, I liked that some questions were the same as in the quizzes, making it worthwhile to do them, but also having questions not shown elsewhere, making the student think about the questions, not just putting the right answer as he has just done the same question elsewhere".
- "There are plenty of materials and it is good that there are in two groups - recommended and required, otherwise it would too overwhelming".
- "I like that there is combination of reading + listening, also a small quiz after each section helps to take the most important take-home messages. Although I had a feeling in some modules, that there is too much reading/listening at once (not really mixed) - I mean too many small sections of listening behind each other, too many reading sections behind each other".
- "I would welcome some list of abbreviations to have a look if need."
- "I would find it appropriate if the reading materials were split into categories relevant to the topics that are about to be presented and thus the students can follow the reading materials regarding each presentation each time. I believe it would be much easier to keep track of all the material and really understand and remember it".

Course duration

- "Allot 2 months for Module 1 learning and possibly two weeks for Module 2 (not whole day, but half of the day for example)".
- "I propose that the duration of the course be prolonged to give more attention and practicality."

5.2 PILOT COURSE 2: CAREER MANAGEMENT AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP

What learning outcomes did you expect to achieve from the course?

Feedback from the student evaluation questionnaires focused mainly on their need for career guidance (career options/opportunities outside of academia; improving CV and cover letter; acquisition of networking skills; competencies required by the job market) and an interest in acquiring knowledge and tools to improve their entrepreneurial skills and mind-set

What are the three most important things that you have learned as a result of participating in this course?

Students identified the most important things learned as a result of participating in the Career Management and Entrepreneurship course to be the following:

- Career management and job search process (CV, cover letter, interviews, networking, etc.): 42,9%
- Business plan canvas: 25,0%
- Transferable soft skills, entrepreneurial skills and skills management: 14,3%
- Storytelling methods: 14,3%

Respondents also mentioned identification of career alternatives in non-academic sectors and the entrepreneurial mind-set vs the PhD mind-set.

What parts of this course were the most relevant for you?

In line with the most important things learned as a result of participation in the course on Career Management and Entrepreneurship, students considered the following aspects of the course as most relevant for them:

- Career options, job hunting and career development: 29,4%
- Mock interview and CV development: 29,4%
- The business model canvas discussion: 17,7%

Several respondents also highlighted the storytelling methods, the pitch, the information provided on entrepreneurship and the peer discussions.

What parts of this course were the least relevant for you?

35,3% of students did not identify any aspects of the course as least relevant.

47,1% of students responded that the least relevant parts of the course was the general information on entrepreneurship and the entrepreneurial mind-set.

Other 17,8% of the students did not refer to any specific part of the course but pointed out that “time management in the course could be improved” (“there was not enough time to finish the asynchronous part before the synchronous”; “the time dedicated to each student's presentation was not equilibrated”).

How can we improve these aspects of the course? Comments/suggestions regarding course methodology, course content and/or learning materials. Additional comments/suggestions.

In general, students seemed to be quite satisfied with the course and did not make many suggestions for general course improvement. The responses have been grouped into the following categories: interaction; course content; learning materials; course duration.

Interaction

- “Hopefully the course can be taught on site in the future. The exchange with fellow students was very valuable but limited by the video format”.
- “It might be better to divide participants into several groups based on their majors (for example, engineering, social sciences, etc.) and have them work on different types of assignments”.
- “Longer interactions on how to improve the CV and cover letters”.

Couse content

- “Make the entrepreneurship part more diverse and have tracks for people in different situation”.
- “For the entrepreneurship part, it would be useful to invite someone who has become a successful entrepreneur and can tell their story, with the opportunity to ask questions”.
- “Could the exercises on entrepreneurship be more adapted for personal level? Instead of creating a sustainable business model, maybe creating a sustainable ecosystem around the research that the student works on would make more sense”.
- “I would only change the content related to entrepreneurship, making it more general”.
- “Change the focus of the entrepreneurship part, making it more targeted to doctoral researchers”.
- “More presentations about Business Examples, Start-Ups, Marketing, etc.”.
- “More storytelling exercises in the face-to-face part”.
- “The Moodle content should be shared sooner so that students can finish it before the practical part”.
- “More guests from industry”.
- “Testimonials from invited speakers that have recently and similarly diverged from academia to the industry”.

Learning materials

- “Perhaps a bit less online videos next time”
- “More materials on storytelling could be included in the online component”.
- “Creating an actual business building model that is compulsory for all students to complete so they can understand the process of turning an idea into money, of what it takes to build a business”.
- “The reason why I did not understand the usefulness of the sustainability part was perhaps that it was the self-study week and we did not have the webinar. So perhaps if we had had the webinar and we would have talked about the issue, then I would have understood the usefulness of the topic for me”.

Course duration

- “More time for the online part”.
- “Regarding the synchronous, the time management should be more effective, taking into consideration the time available and the number of students, so that all have the same time to practice, present and receive feedback”.

5.3 PILOT COURSE 3: SUPERVISION

What learning outcomes did you expect to achieve from the course?

The course was designed with the objective of streamlining the management of PhD supervisors at the piloting universities, create a forum for discussion, identify relevant aspects of doctoral studies and enhance quality in supervision practices.

The course aimed specifically to:

- Provide crucial information on the institutional frames, resources, and guidelines for supervisory practices;
- Discuss essential pedagogical issues, as well as the widening research skills that are part and parcel of supervision;
- Help supervisors to integrate their own research mission into supervision practices;
- Break the solitude of supervision perceived as master-apprentice practice behind closed doors, and encourage a more collegial, shared supervision and peer support culture;
- Help participants to identify key tensions and dynamics, to reflect on local practices;
- Provide tools and practical resources for participants to develop their own skills and well-being further as supervisors.

What are the three most important things that you have learned as a result of participating in this course?

Students believed that the most important things that they learned in the course on Supervision were:

- Supervision roles, models, tools, resources and practices: 43,3%
- Importance of communication/dialogue and active listening in the supervision process: 23,3%
- Exchange of experiences/good practices with colleagues and peers: 20,0%
- Importance of devoting attention not only to “the end result (articles and the thesis)” but also to the students’ learning process, career development and general well-being: 13,3%

What parts of this course were the most relevant for you?

Students highlighted the group discussions as the most relevant aspect of the course on Supervision, with a special focus on the peer discussion groups and brain-storming sessions 27,7%.

Other aspects that were considered as most relevant were:

- Identification of the nature and challenges of supervision: 17,0%
- Normative issues regarding doctoral education: 17,0%
- Responsible and ethical conduct / code of good practices: 12,7%
- The learning materials provided (readings, practical examples, videos and zoom lectures): 8,5%

What parts of this course were the least relevant for you?

17,0% of respondents stated that all parts of the course were relevant.

23,4% of respondents considered that the normative issues were the least relevant, as they are not only easily accessible on university and government websites, but also may change over time.

Other respondents referred to career issues and perspectives with the non-academic sector (“it would be best directed at the doctoral students”).

Several respondents believed that the group discussions were more relevant for “colleagues with more seniority” ... “as most of us were very inexperienced supervisors and we could not give very useful advice, just our point of view”.

How can we improve these aspects of the course? Comments/suggestions regarding course methodology, course content and/or learning materials. Additional comments/suggestions.

Although participants expressed their satisfaction with the course, only 6,4% did not make any suggestions for further course development and/or improvement.

The remaining 93,6% of participants made numerous suggestions for general course improvement. The responses have been grouped into the following categories: student profile; interaction; course content; learning materials and methods; course duration.

Student profile

- "Since participants came from very different disciplines, the problems and solutions addresses were not always applicable to others".
- "Maybe the course should be tailored to different doctoral schools, or at least thematic bundles of them (it is not very useful to have exchanges between medical researchers and gamification researchers, the context and practices are so different)".

Interaction

- "More peer-to-peer discussions".
- "More space for discussing and creating time and space for reflection and exchange of information".
- "This kind of education should be held face-to-face".
- "I would like to meet in smaller, multilingual and multicultural groups".
- "Perhaps more debate among the attendees about specific examples of problems that can occur when directing or co-directing a doctoral thesis would have been enriching".

Course content

- "I would have liked to have some contents that engaged more critically the practice of supervision".
- "Include sessions on leadership and motivation".
- "More practical case studies".

Learning materials and methods

- "High-level, too abstract material"
- "More practical examples instead of "nice sounding" abstract/high-level and generic material".
- "Sometimes, the slides contained too much information and it was a bit difficult to follow".
- "Sessions could focus less on going through slides (they could be shared beforehand) and more on sharing of experiences".
- "Perhaps more variation and rhythm amidst each session, e.g., smaller group meetings, videos, discussions after the watching".
- "Too many videos!! They are definitely not the best material to utilize in teaching".
- "Less videos, more articles for reading".
- "More team exercises, less writing".
- "Moodle page is not clear".
- "Too much homework".

Course duration

- "A little bit longer course?"

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- "It was very short, especially for a senior workshop. Many aspects could be addressed in greater depth."
- "It could be a little longer and with a little more practical exercises".
- "The live sessions were quite long and one gets quite tired afterwards. I would arrange one more session but shorten each session".
- "Perhaps shorter sessions, but a few more".
- "The duration of the sessions could be extended by half an hour".
- "Extending the duration of the course so that there are no problems in finishing/seeing all the aspects".

6. COLLABORATION BETWEEN UNIVERSITIES AND THE NON-ACADEMIC SECTOR IN DOCTORAL EDUCATION

Course participants were asked what they consider to be the key issues regarding collaboration between universities and the non-academic sector in doctoral education, based on their personal experiences in doctoral education activities and in the pilot course taken.

96,5% of students responded.

Of the responses received, 9,6% said that they could not or did not know how to answer this question due to a lack of experience in the non-academic sector.

41,9% of respondents expressed their views with regards to collaboration between the academic and non-academic sectors in doctoral education:

- “There should be more joint projects. It is a great opportunity for any student to deal with an actual problem from the private sector.”
- “There is a need to build up a network outside academia, stimulating university-industry dialogue, enhancing employability perspectives of PhD candidates and holders.”
- “Short internships for doctoral students in companies - trying different positions – would be beneficial.”
- “PhD students should be given the opportunity to engage in activities not directly related to their dissertation, especially if those activities require them to interact with non-academic stakeholders/ partners and to explain the value of their research to a non-specialist audience. This seems to be especially difficult with Arts, Humanities and (to a lesser extent) Social Science students.”

- “It can be challenging to get non-academic representatives to commit to long-term activities which help shape doctoral education if their initial experiences suggest that doctoral students are uninterested in that engagement (for example, when they commit time to information-sharing and networking events and students simply don’t register or don’t attend).”
- “Input from non-academic sector representatives, in terms of shaping the training which doctoral students receive, is a long-term investment which could provide a pool of more suitable employees/ collaborators, but short-term priorities often take precedence.”
- “PhD supervisors should know that part of their role (even if it isn’t formally stated) is to prepare their students for a range of potential careers, or at least to facilitate this if they don’t feel able to give wider career advice. This includes legitimising and encouraging non-academic collaboration for their students.”
- “Students should know the differences between work in the academic and non-academic sectors.”
- “I would like supervisors to be more aware of the life outside academia. Perhaps there should be a recommendation that one of the supervisors should be outside the academia. Now supervisors do not or cannot really give advice on the life after graduation, except that I should apply for funding. The non-academic career is not really being discussed.”
- “Breach the gap between academia and non-academic sectors, by allowing students to do internships early on, or more engaging workshops between both parties”.
- “Strengthen interaction with companies and enable students to spend a short internship in industry would be important. However, often companies do not consider this as “useful” and are hesitating to host students”.
- “The key issue regarding collaboration between universities and the non/academic sector in doctoral education is to define the roles. The collaboration should be beneficial for both sides and can be used to show the young doctoral students how they can apply their knowledge and build a successful career in the non-academic sector.”
- “I think it is necessary to make doctoral programs known to companies, encourage work related to the business world in real solutions. PhDs should be well received in the business world.”
- “Promote the participation of the non-academic sector in doctoral education.”
- “Promote industrial PhD programs.”
- “It is necessary to make sure the doctoral student can achieve both academic training and industrial experience and capabilities.”
- “Make graduate students aware of the skills and knowledge they have acquired at the university and their ability to apply them in the non-academic or professional sector.”

Another 40,7% of respondents referred to the lack of communication and alignment between the orientations, expectations, standards and work cultures in the academic and non-academic sectors.

- “The different aims of those two sectors - universities and research in general strive to push global knowledge further, while the non-academic sector aims to make one bigger breakthrough and make money from it.”

- "I would say that a key issue regarding collaboration between universities and the non-academic sector in doctoral education is perhaps time constraints in reference to the delivery of results. Since doctoral students are accustomed to spending a considerable amount of time on their research project before producing an article, they may be unable to achieve adequate/meaningful results if it is a short-term collaboration."
- "The university is primarily an education- and research-focused institution whilst the private sector is usually output-focused."
- "Universities are often not enough open to cooperating with the non-academic sector, or there is no basis for it in form of core or open access facilities that can bring both sectors together."
- "The mentality in academia and non-academia is very different. People in academia often have no connection to industry and therefore little experience in this area. Also, the network mostly consists of academic contacts made at conferences. This lack of experience and connections to the non-academic sector is the biggest problem in collaboration."
- "I think we should promote more articulation with industry."
- "One key issue that is naturally common to encounter is the fact that the involved parts have a rather different vision of what is the aim and how it should be achieved."
- "Different expectations from academia and industry as regarding the "gain" from the collaboration."
- "Differences in collaboration goals."
- "It takes time to build understanding on the shared goals of collaboration."
- "We lack exposure to the non-academic sector."
- "I would say that, at least in the field of biomedicine, collaborating with companies is not easy. I think this is partly because the bioscience companies perform their own basic research, so they do not have to rely on the universities. On the other hand, this is different in the IT field, where companies collaborate continuously with universities."
- "Lack of awareness on the part of the private sector regarding what research is, especially on the part of SMEs."
- "Mutual knowledge of the activities carried out in each sector and how to be complementary and how to resolve possible conflicts of interest."

11,6% of respondents referred to data sharing, IPR and licencing as key issues for collaboration between the academic and non-academic sectors:

- "Making formal agreements (financial, confidentiality, IP Rights etc.)."
- "Even if both parties agree on patenting, the issue of IP comes to play."
- "The manipulation and shareability of data is always an issue to be taken care of. All involved parties should state clearly their position on these aspects and researchers, as producers and analysers of data, should obtain clear guidelines of how to do so and follow them no matter how time consuming it can be. And if later we are to give such guidelines we should be able to explain how the FAIR principles should be used, so that our research and data are as open as possible, as closed as necessary."
- "In my opinion, the key issue is the openness of datasets and licenses between non-academic and academic environments."

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- “The ownership of the data produced and therefore the rights to use it.”
- “For me, possibly the largest issue is the matter of intellectual property. There seems to be an ongoing pattern of private sector entities being wary (perhaps justifiably so) of cooperating with academia, for fear of their current IP leaking in some form, and the newly created one ending up out of their control. There are of course NDAs, but there seem to be grey areas even within those.”
- “Intellectual property (IP) issues can be an obstacle to e.g. publish the outcomes of a collaboration between university and industry. On the other hand, doctoral students need to publish papers in order to obtain the PhD.”
- “In my experience the question of intellectual property is decisive on whether a collaboration happens or not. As doctoral students we aim to publish but depending on the industry partner, it may not be wished.”

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7. ANNEX I: EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRES

7.1. STUDENT QUESTIONNAIRE

PILOT COURSE EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE: STUDENTS

The purpose of this questionnaire is to evaluate the pilot course you have participated in and to be able to introduce those modifications needed in order to improve its quality. By responding to this questionnaire, you agree that DocEnhance will process the information provided for the purpose stated above.

Course name: -

Course dates:

University

1) What learning outcomes did you expect to achieve from the course?

2) To what degree did you achieve your expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all, 6: completely)

1	2	3	4	5	6

3) What are the three most important things that you have learned as a result of participating in this course:

1.
2.
3.

4) What parts of this course were the most relevant for you? Why?

5) What parts of this course were the least relevant for you? Why?

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6) How can we improve these aspects of the course?

7) In your opinion, to what extent are the course guidelines, work methods, course content and learning materials adapted to your expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all, 6 = completely)

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Course Guidelines						
Work Methods						
Course Content						
Learning Materials						

8) Comments/suggestions regarding course methodology, course content and/or learning materials

9) How much time and effort did you need to achieve the course objectives? (1: very little, 6: too much)

1	2	3	4	5	6

10) Do you think that the learning outcomes of the course will be useful for your future career development? (1: not at all, 6: completely)

1	2	3	4	5	6

11) Please give the course an overall assessment. (1: very poor, 6: excellent)

1	2	3	4	5	6

12) Would you recommend this course to other students?

Yes	No
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13) Based on your experiences in doctoral education activities and in this course, what do you consider to be the key issues regarding collaboration between universities and the non-academic sector in doctoral education?

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14) Additional comments/suggestions

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Thank you for your feedback!

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7.2 SUPERVISORS QUESTIONNAIRE

PILOT COURSE EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE: SUPERVISORS

The purpose of this questionnaire is to evaluate the pilot course you have participated in and to be able to introduce those modifications needed in order to improve its quality. By responding to this questionnaire, you agree that DocEnhance will process the information provided for the purpose stated above.

Course name: _____

Course dates: _____

University _____

Expected outcomes of the training: _____

1) In your opinion, how well did you achieve the expected outcomes of the training? (1: very poorly, 6: very well)

1	2	3	4	5	6

2) What are the three most important things that you have learned as a result of participating in this training:

1.
2.
3.

3) What parts of this training were the most relevant for you? Why?

--

4) What parts of this training were the least relevant for you? Why?

--

5) How can we improve these aspects of the training?

--

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6) In your opinion, to what extent are the training guidelines, work methods, training content and materials adapted to the expected outcomes of the training? (1: not at all, 6 = completely)

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Training Guidelines						
Work Methods						
Training Content						
Training Materials						

7) Comments/suggestions regarding training methodology, content and/or materials

8) How much time and effort did you need to achieve the training objectives? (1: very little, 6: very much)

1	2	3	4	5	6

9) How useful do you think that the training outcomes of the course will be for your future supervision activities? (1: very little, 6: very much)

1	2	3	4	5	6

10) Please give the training an overall assessment. (1: below average, 5: excellent)

1	2	3	4	5	6

11) Would you recommend this course to other supervisors?

Yes	No

12) Based on your experiences in doctoral education activities and in this training, what do you consider to be the key issues regarding collaboration between universities and the non-academic sector in doctoral education? Please, mention at least three issues with short explanations.

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13) Additional comments/suggestions

Thank you for your feedback!

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7.3. EDUCATORS/FACULTY QUESTIONNAIRE

PILOT COURSE EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE: EDUCATORS/FACULTY

The purpose of this questionnaire is to evaluate the pilot course you have participated in and to be able to introduce those modifications needed in order to improve its quality. By responding to this questionnaire, you agree that DocEnhance will process the information provided for the purpose stated above.

Course name: _____

Course dates: _____

University _____

1) Were you involved in the course design?

Yes	No

2) What learning outcomes did you expect students to achieve from the course?

3) To what degree do you think that students achieved the expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all, 6: completely)

1	2	3	4	5	6

4) In your opinion, what are the three most important things that students learned as a result of participating in this course:

1.	
2.	
3.	

5) What parts of this course do you think were the most relevant for students? Why?

6) What parts of this course do you think were the least relevant for students? Why?

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7) How can we improve these aspects of the course?

8) In your opinion, to what extent were the course guidelines, work methods, course content and learning materials adapted to the expected learning outcomes? (1: not at all, 6 = completely)

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Course Guidelines						
Work Methods						
Course Content						
Learning Materials						

9) Did you need to make adaptations to the work methods, course content or learning materials? If so, what adaptations and why?

10) Comments/suggestions regarding course methodology, course content and/or learning materials

11) Please give the course an overall assessment. (1: very poor, 6: excellent)

1	2	3	4	5	6

12) Based on your experiences in doctoral education activities and in this course, what do you consider to be the key issues regarding collaboration between universities and the non-academic sector in doctoral education?

13) Additional comments/suggestions

Thank you for your feedback!

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7.4. ORGANISERS QUESTIONNAIRE

PILOT COURSE EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE: ORGANISERS

The purpose of this questionnaire is to evaluate the pilot course you have participated in and to be able to introduce those modifications needed in order to improve its quality. By responding to this questionnaire, you agree that DocEnhance will process the information provided for the purpose stated above.

Course name: _____

Course dates: _____

University _____

1) Were you involved in the course design?

Yes	No

2) Did your university need to adapt the course design to meet specific needs or requirements?

Yes	No

3) If so, what did you need to adapt and why?

Course Guidelines	
Work Methods	
Course Content	
Learning Materials	

4) How interested were teachers and students in the new course offering? (1: not at all, 6: very interested)

1	2	3	4	5	6

5) How did you source teachers for the course?

Internal staff members	
External educators/consultants	

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Industrial/Business partners	
Other (please specify)	

6) How were students recruited?

7) Did you encounter any difficulties or constraints when organizing the pilot course? If so, please specify.

8) Are you satisfied with the piloting results? (1: not at all, 6: completely)

1	2	3	4	5	6

9) In your opinion, what could be improved?

10) How will the course be embedded in your university's doctoral education offerings after pilot delivery?

11) Based on your experiences in doctoral education activities and in this course, what do you consider to be the key issues regarding collaboration between universities and the non-academic sector in doctoral education?

12) Additional comments/suggestions

Thank you for your feedback!